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Chemical Behaviour of some Metal Complexes of O and N Donor Ligands

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THE coordination chemistry of hydrazine and substituted-hydrazines is of special interest because of the variety of ways in which these species can be bonded to the metal ions^{1,2}. In continuation to the previous work^{3,4}, the present paper describes preparation and characterisation of the Co^{II} and Ni^{II} complexes of 2-benzoylpyridine benzoylhydrazone (BH), 2-(acetylamino)benzoic acid (AB) and 2-(benzoylamino)benzoic acid (BB).

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of reagent grade. Benzoylhydrazine⁵ and 2-benzoylpyridine benzoylhydrazone (BH)⁶ were prepared by reported methods. The ligands, AB and BB were prepared by the standard methods^{7,8}. The sodium salts were prepared by mixing an ethereal solution of the ligand and methanolic solution of the sodium in equimolar ratio.

The complexes of ligand BH were prepared by mixing and refluxing the aqueous solution of the metal chloride and ethanolic solution of the ligand for ~2 h. The complexes separated out in the form of precipitates, which were filtered, washed with ethanol and dried in vacuum over P₄O₁₀. The metal complexes of the ligand AB and BB were prepared by mixing and heating the aqueous solution of metal salt and sodium salt of the ligand (1:2) on a water-bath for ~1 h. Crystals of the complexes so formed were filtered, washed with ethanol and dried in vacuum over P₄O₁₀.

The elemental analyses were carried out at C.D.R.I., Lucknow. Magnetic susceptibility were measured on the powdered forms of the complexes on a Gouy balance. The metal contents were determined by standard methods⁹. Conductance measurements (in DMF) were made using a Digisun D1-909 digital conductivity meter. The thermal data of the complexes were recorded at G. N. Dev University, Amritsar. The ir and electronic spectra were obtained from I.I.T., Madras.

Results and Discussion

The complexes are characterised on the basis of elemental analysis, magnetic moment, conductivity, thermal studies, ir and electronic spectra. Formulae of the complexes have been justified on the basis of elemental analyses (Table 1). All the complexes gave very low molar conductance values in DMF (5–20 Ω cm² mol⁻¹) suggesting that they are non-electrolytes (Table 1). The thermograms of Co^{II} and Ni^{II} complexes with ligands AB and BB show initial mass loss in the temperature range 140–225° corresponding to the loss of two water molecules. The expulsion of water molecules in the above range of temperatures indicates that the water molecules are coordinated¹⁰. The presence of water molecule is further evidenced by their DTA curves which give endothermic peaks in the temperature range 155–200°. The sharp decomposition associated with the loss of ligand starts above 270° and the final products of the decomposition are the metallic oxides.

The ir bands at 1 670 and 1 590 cm⁻¹ in the spectrum of BH are assigned to $\nu_{C=O}$ and ν_{C-N} , respectively. In the Ni^{II} complexes of BH, sharp bands at ~1 585 cm⁻¹ are found which confirms the presence of C=N–N=C structure¹¹. This shows that the ligand functions as tridentate monobasic (NNO) donor, coordinating through pyridine nitrogen, azomethine nitrogen and enolic oxygen¹¹. In Co^{II} complexes, a strong band at 1 620 cm⁻¹ appears which indicates the coordination through keto-oxygen, the ligand behaving as a neutral tridentate (NNO) donor¹¹. The ir spectra of AB and BB show a band at 2 590 cm⁻¹ assigned to ν_{OH} of carboxylic group. The C=O and C–OH stretching modes occurring at about 1 700 and 1 330 cm⁻¹, respectively^{12,13} are replaced by two new bands at about 1 540 and 1 370 cm⁻¹ due to $\nu_{as}(COO^-)$ and $\nu_s(COO^-)$, respectively¹⁴. The ν_{N-H} appearing at 3 395 and 3 465 cm⁻¹ in AB and BB, respectively, undergoes negative shift by 155–190 cm⁻¹ in the complexes indicating the coordination of the nitrogen of amide group. The N–H bands in complexes are somewhat obscured by ν_{O-H} mode of water of crystallisation¹⁵. The $\nu_{C=O}$ of the amide group at 1 630 cm⁻¹ remains unchanged ruling out coordination through amide oxygen.

The magnetic moment of Ni^{II} complexes observed at room temperature is in the range 2.9–3.19 B.M. (Table 1), which indicates that the complexes are pseudo-octahedral. The cobalt

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TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA AND LIGAND FIELD PARAMETERS

Compd	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)		ΔM $\Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$	μ_{eff} B.M.	$Dq(E)$	$Dq(A)$	Dt	$-Ds$
	M	N						
Ni(BH) ₃	8.61 (8.90)	12.39 (12.65)	5	2.9	1 120	900	126	—
Ni(AB) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂	12.97 (13.02)	6.01 (6.21)	8	3.19	1 165	802	200	—
Ni(BB) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂	10.16 (10.21)	4.60 (4.87)	7	3.11	1 180	776	231	—
Co(BH)Cl ₂	13.18 (13.60)	9.43 (9.70)	15	4.86	1 131	718	236	1 366
Co(AB) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂	12.98 (13.06)	6.15 (6.37)	20	4.79	1 194	753	252	1 430
Co(BB) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂	9.96 (10.24)	5.01 (4.86)	18	5.10	1 220	771	257	1 652

complexes show high-spin octahedral configuration as the values lie in the range 4.97–5.10 B.M.¹⁶

In the electronic spectra of Ni^{II} complexes, four bands have been observed at 9 900–10 100, 10 730–11 800, 17 800–18 600 and 28 300–29 400 cm⁻¹ regions. The first two bands are the split components of ν_1 and consequently can be assigned to the transitions ${}^3B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^3E_g$ (ν_1) and ${}^3B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^3B_{2g}$ (ν_1). The remaining two bands have been assigned to ${}^3B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F)$ (ν_2) and ${}^3B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P)$ (ν_3) and are not greatly affected by the low symmetry environment on account of the fact that the levels concerned are ${}^3T_{1g}(F)$ and ${}^3T_{1g}(P)$ terms, which give rise to (${}^3A_{2g} + {}^3E_g$) in D_{4h} symmetry. In almost all the cases, only ν_1 has been found to split. Ligand field parameters $Dq(E)$ and Dt have been evaluated⁶ (Table 1). The distorted octahedral stereochemistry is further supported by the ratio ν_2/ν_1 which comes out to be 1.5–1.6, whereas the ratio in octahedral complexes¹⁷ should be about 1.8.

Octahedral cobalt(II) ion has the ground terms ${}^4T_{1g}$; three transitions are usually observed in its complexes ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(F)$ (ν_1); ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4A_{2g}(F)$ (ν_2) and ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)$ (ν_3). In lower symmetry D_{4h} , the ν_1 band is observed to split into two components¹⁸ (${}^4B_{2g}$, 4E_g) which depends upon the extent of magnitude of distortion produced by axial ligands. The ν_2 is also expected to split into ${}^4A_{2g}$ and ${}^4E_g(P)$. The ν_3 transition in octahedral stereochemistry transforms to ${}^4B_{1g}$ in D_{4h} symmetry and this transition is sometimes observed. The electronic spectra of Co^{II} complexes show bands in the region 6 370–7 270 (ν_1) and 8 580–9 250 cm⁻¹ (ν_2) accompanied by a shoulder in most of the cases in the region 15 040–17 240 cm⁻¹ and the third transition ν_3 has been found to split in all the complexes and their absorption bands appear in the 17 290–18 600 and 20 620–23 810 cm⁻¹ regions. These transitions have been assigned on the basis of D_{4h} symmetry. From these bands, radial parameters Ds and Dt have been evaluated. $Dq(E)$ has also been calculated (Table 1). The ratio ν_2/ν_1 being about 1.2, is a good evidence for pseudo-octahedral geometry¹⁹.

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Stability Constants of Neodymium(III) Complexes with 8-Hydroxyquinoline and its Derivatives

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THE paper describes the complex formation of Nd^{III} with 8-hydroxyquinoline (OX), 8-hydroxyquinoline-5-sulphonic acid (OSA), 7-iodo-8-hydroxyquinoline-5-sulphonic acid (IOSA), 5-nitro-8-hydroxyquinoline (NSOX), 5,7-dinitro-8-hydroxyquinoline